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CBS-37: DEVELOPMENT AND PSYCHOMETRIC PROPERTIES OF COUPLE BURNOUT SCALE

Paulina Quiroz-Díaz¹, Nayely Carrión-Encarnación², Leonela Leyva-Gonzales³, Marcia Romero-Vásquez⁴ and Carlos Pérez-Lara⁵

¹Cesar Vallejo University, Email: paquirozd@ucvvirtual.edu.pe Orcid ID: orcid.org/0000-0002-4520-5080

²Cesar Vallejo University, Orcid ID: orcid.org/0000-0002-5561-1621

³Cesar Vallejo University, Orcid ID: orcid.org/0000-0003-3674-117X

⁴Cesar Vallejo University, Orcid ID: orcid.org/0000-0002-5632-048X

⁵Cesar Vallejo University, Orcid ID: orcid.org/0000-0002-5712-2186

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ABSTRACT

Couple burnout refers to the emotional, mental, and physical exhaustion that arises from ongoing difficulties or tensions within a romantic relationship. The primary objective of the present study was to develop and evaluate the psychometric properties of the Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37) for Young Adults, 2025 edition. Methods: This was an instrumental study, as it focused on examining the psychometric properties of a newly developed assessment instrument. A total of 500 young adults, both men and women aged between 18 and 45 years, participated in the study. Results: Exploratory factor analysis identified three dimensions: Indifference, Reduction in Sexual Intimacy, and Unmet Expectations. Confirmatory factor analysis indicated that the multidimensional model demonstrated adequate fit (CFI = 0.91; RMSEA = 0.07; SRMR = 0.04; AIC = 20853.38). Divergent validity was supported by significant negative correlations with the Relationship Satisfaction Scale. Additionally, reliability analysis revealed strong internal consistency, with omega and alpha coefficients ranging from 0.92 to 0.98. Conclusions: The CBS-37 is a self-report instrument designed to assess couple burnout, demonstrating satisfactory psychometric properties.

KEYWORDS: Couple Burnout; Indifference; Decline in Sexual Intimacy; Unmet Expectations; Young Adults.

1. INTRODUCTION

Couple burnout is a phenomenon that adversely affects romantic relationships due to unresolved difficulties or persistent tensions. When such issues are not properly managed, they can lead to emotional, mental, and physical exhaustion (Batres, 2016; Martínez, 2010). As a result, the relationship may deteriorate or dissolve, significantly impacting the and physical well-being of both partners (Villavicencio & Jaramillo, 2020). According to a report by the World Health Organization (2021), approximately 30% of women have experienced physical or emotional violence in intimate relationships, contributing to emotional exhaustion. This study aligns with Sustainable Development Goal 3: Good Health and Well-being, specifically target 3.4, which aims to identify and prevent unresolved tensions that may lead to severe consequences, such as violence or mental health deterioration. Based on this context, couple burnout emerges from unresolved relational stressors, resulting in exhaustion, conflict, and separation.

Reported data indicate that 37% of couples in Asia have experienced violence, highlighting how unresolved emotional and physical exhaustion can escalate into abusive dynamics if not addressed in time (González et al., 2021). In Europe, between 20% and 50% of couples report emotional burnout, particularly in long-term relationships. In Spain, for example, surveys show a widespread perception of relationship deterioration over time (Lila, 2010). In Mexico, emotional and physical exhaustion has been cited as a contributing factor in partner breakups (Rodríguez, 2022), while in Chile, university students have identified relationship burnout as a consequence of partner violence (Póo & Vizcarra, 2008). Similarly, in Peru, 63.2% of women aged 15 to 49 have experienced some form of partner violence, indicating widespread relationship deterioration (INEL, 2020). Understanding this variable is crucial due to its profound psychological and social implications, including its potential to escalate into violence and the eventual dissolution of relationships.

Currently, there are no instruments specifically designed to measure couple burnout. Existing tools focus on general psychological states within relationships. For example, the Triangular Love Scale (ETAS), developed by Sternberg in 1986, assesses intimacy, passion, and commitment, emphasizing the positive aspects of love but not the negative elements contributing to relationship decline (Ventura & Caycho, 2016). The Dyadic Adjustment Scale (DAS) measures relationship quality through

four subscales: consensus, satisfaction, affectional expression, and cohesion—but does not specifically assess burnout, limiting its usefulness for evaluating emotional and physical exhaustion in couples (Moral de la Rubia, 2009). The Emotional Burnout Scale (ECE), designed for university students, measures emotional exhaustion but does not focus on romantic relationships (Ramírez, 2007). Lastly, the Couple Dependency Scale (SED) measures emotional dependence in current or past relationships but fails to account for other factors that influence relational dynamics (Camarillo et al., 2020).

This new instrument defines couple burnout as the emotional, mental, and physical exhaustion resulting from relational tensions or conflicts, manifested through feelings of powerlessness, declining health, loss of energy, and avoidant or hostile behaviors (Batres, 2016; Martínez, 2010). The scale consists of four dimensions:

Indifference: Characterized by frequent devaluation or contempt expressed through non-constructive criticism, insults, humiliation, and threats, undermining emotional integrity (Camarillo et al., 2020).

Deteriorated Communication: Ineffective or confusing interaction patterns that erode emotional connection and generate misunderstandings and mistrust.

Reduction in Sexual Intimacy: As defined by García (2002), limitations in physical intimacy and imbalance in decision-making power affect relational satisfaction.

Unmet Expectations: Expectations are fundamental in partner selection and, when unmet in marriage or cohabitation, often lead to conflict and relationship breakdown (Galindo, 2002).

Regarding psychometric properties, according to the American Educational Research Association and the American Psychological Association (American Educational Research Association et al., 2020), these refer to the aspects that determine the accuracy and usefulness of a psychological test or assessment tool. These characteristics ensure that the instrument reliably and accurately measures what it is intended to assess. Validity, on the other hand, refers to the evidence supporting that the instrument truly measures what it claims to measure, thus providing a scientific basis that justifies its use for a specific purpose. This validity is classified into different types. Content validity is a procedure used in research and evaluation in which a panel of experts in a given field is selected to analyze, evaluate, and provide well-founded judgments about an instrument. Construct validity, determined through

factor analysis, involves identifying underlying structures from observable variables, grouping them into dimensions or factors to simplify analysis. Divergent validity indicates that a measurement instrument is not assessing constructs different from the one it is intended to measure. In other words, it demonstrates that the test appropriately distinguishes between different concepts. Reliability refers to the stability and consistency of scores across equivalent versions of a test, assuming that one administration does not affect performance on another. In general, a reliable instrument should yield consistent and predictable results, regardless of the method used to assess it, such as reliability coefficients, standard error, or Item Response Theory (IRT).

Given this context, the study poses the following research question: Are the psychometric properties of the Couple Burnout Scale for Young Adults (2025) adequate?

In terms of justification, this study serves a practical purpose by enabling psychology professionals to assess couple burnout in young adults, thereby facilitating the design of intervention programs or treatment plans tailored to this population. From a methodological perspective, it contributes a psychometric instrument supported by evidence of validity and reliability for measuring

couple burnout in young adults.

The general objective of the study was to construct and evaluate the psychometric properties of the Couple Burnout Scale for Young Adults (2025). The specific objectives were as follows: (1) to establish content validity through expert judgment; (2) to determine construct validity through exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis; (3) to determine evidence of divergent validity by correlating the Couple Attrition Scale with the results of the Couple Satisfaction Scale (ESP-10), and (4) to determine the reliability of the Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37) using Cronbach's alpha coefficient.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1. Study Design

This research follows an instrumental design aimed at developing a multidimensional scale to assess couple burnout in young adults, ensuring the tool's psychometric validity and reliability in accordance with the standards of the American Educational Research Association and the American Psychological Association (2020).

2.2. Procedure And Participants

The study was conducted in three consecutive phases, as outlined in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Workflow For The Development And Psychometric Evaluation Of The Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37).

(A) Phase One: Item Development

In the initial phase, a preliminary version of the

Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37) was constructed. This process began with an extensive literature review of related instruments, leading to a conceptual definition of "couple burnout" and the identification of its theoretical dimensions. Based on this, 60 preliminary items were created twice the number of items planned for the final version as recommended by Kline (2023). A panel of expert judges subsequently reviewed these items for content validity and relevance, resulting in a reduced set of 51 items.

(B) Phase Two: Content Validity Of The CBS-37 Items

In the second phase, content validity was assessed using the expert judgment method, involving five specialists in mental health (clinical psychologists with at least a master's degree and five years of experience in couples therapy), in line with the standards of the American Educational Research Association and the American Psychological Association (2020). Items were evaluated for clarity, coherence, and relevance. The statistical analysis using Aiken's V yielded values up to 1.00, indicating strong content validity. Based on expert feedback, 3 items were eliminated, resulting in 48 items. Subsequent exploratory factor analysis (EFA) led to the removal of 11 additional items, producing a final version with 37 items. The scale used a five-point Likert response format ranging from 1 ("Never") to 5 ("Always"). Dimensional scores were calculated by summing the responses for each subscale.

(C) Phase Three: Psychometric Property Evaluation

In the third phase, the scale's psychometric properties convergent and construct validity, as well as reliability – were assessed. A total sample of 500 young adults aged 18–45 ($M = 23$, $SD = 7.63$) participated, with women comprising 65.2% of the sample. To ensure data quality, participants were required to be in a romantic relationship and sexually active. Cases with incomplete, inconsistent, or implausible responses were excluded. The sample was randomly split into two subgroups ($n = 250$ each): one for exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and the other for confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). The age distributions were comparable (EFA: $M = 23.0$, $SD = 7.80$; CFA: $M = 22.0$, $SD = 7.44$), in line with methodological recommendations (Field, 2013; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013).

Participants were recruited via a Google Forms survey distributed on social media (WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram). To reduce social desirability

bias, the link was shared in general-interest online spaces, with permission sought where necessary. Participation was voluntary and anonymous, with no financial incentives. Participants received clear instructions emphasizing the importance of honest responses. Informed consent was obtained electronically. Alongside the CBS-37, the Couple Satisfaction Scale (ESP-10) was administered via the same link.

All responses were reviewed for quality, and no questionnaires were excluded, yielding a final sample of 500 valid cases.

2.3. Measures

2.3.1. Couple Burnout Scale (Cbs-37)

The Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37) was developed to assess emotional, mental, and physical exhaustion within romantic relationships, stemming from unresolved tensions or difficulties. Burnout is expressed through feelings of helplessness, deteriorating health, loss of energy, and avoidant or hostile behaviors (Batres, 2016; Martínez, 2010). The final version of the scale consists of 37 items, scored on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ("Never") to 5 ("Always"). The scale includes three dimensions: Indifference (Items 1–9): Captures emotional detachment, devaluation, and hostile or invalidating communication. Reduction in Sexual Intimacy (Items 10–21): Assesses the reduction in physical closeness, affection, and desire. Unmet Expectations (Items 22–37): Measures the discrepancy between expectations and relational reality. The total score is calculated by summing the scores of each item. Higher scores indicate greater burnout in the corresponding dimension. The scale demonstrated high internal consistency across all dimensions.

2.3.2. Couple Satisfaction Scale (Esp-10)

The Couple Satisfaction Scale (ESP-10) was developed by González-Rivera in collaboration with psychology students from the Carlos Albizu University in Puerto Rico. It aims to measure the degree of satisfaction within romantic relationships through a unidimensional approach. Satisfaction is conceptualized as a person's perception either positive or negative of their relationship, based on the fulfillment of personal needs and expectations of an ideal partnership (González-Rivera & Veray-Alicea, 2018). The instrument comprises 10 items rated on a four-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ("Never") to 4 ("Always"). As it is a unidimensional scale, all items contribute to a single overall score. Higher scores indicate greater satisfaction in the relationship.

2.4. Statistical Analysis

To assess the normality and adequacy of the data, a descriptive analysis was conducted on the items of the Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37). Measures such as means, variances, skewness, and kurtosis were calculated using SPSS version 30 (George & Mallery, 2020). Additionally, Mardia's test for multivariate normality was applied, with p -values > 0.05 considered indicative of a normal distribution. Sampling adequacy for exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was evaluated using Bartlett's test of sphericity and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) index, performed in JASP (version 0.19.3.0; Love et al., 2019).

The EFA was conducted using a polychoric correlation matrix and the minimum residuals (MinRes) extraction method with oblique (Oblimin) rotation appropriate for correlated factors enhancing interpretability and model fit (Lloret-Segura et al., 2014; Ferrando & Lorenzo-Seva, 2014). KMO values and Bartlett's test results indicated that the data were suitable for factor analysis (Kaiser, 1974; Bartlett, 1954). Items with factor loadings below 0.40 were excluded (Hair et al., 2019). The resulting structure comprised three dimensions: Indifference, Decline in Physical Intimacy, and Loss of Satisfaction due to Unmet Expectations. All EFA procedures were conducted using JASP (version 0.19.3.0) (Love et al., 2019).

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was conducted to verify the factorial structure. Model fit was considered acceptable based on the following criteria: non-significant chi-square ($p > .05$), CFI $> .90$, RMSEA and SRMR $< .08$, and a lower AIC indicating better fit (Hu & Bentler, 1999; Kline, 2016). Two models were compared: (i) a unidimensional model and (ii) a three-factor model. CFA was performed

using SPSS 30 and AMOS 30.0 (Arbuckle, 2019; George & Mallery, 2020).

Divergent validity was assessed by calculating correlations between each CBS-37 dimension and the total score of the Couple Satisfaction Scale (ESP-10), as these are commonly referenced instruments in the literature. Analyses were conducted using SPSS version 30.

Reliability was examined using internal consistency coefficients Cronbach's alpha and McDonald's omega (McDonald, 1999; Campo-Arias & Oviedo, 2008)—also analyzed in JASP (version 0.19.3.0).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Content Validity Of The CBS-37

An expert panel evaluated the 60 items of the preliminary test using three criteria: clarity, coherence, and relevance. The analysis of the scores was conducted using Aiken's V statistical test, which yielded $V = 1.00$. Furthermore, the absence of suggestions to add items confirms the comprehensiveness of the instrument. The content validity of the test is strong.

3.2. Descriptive Item Analysis

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the items of the Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37). The results indicate that the data do not follow a normal distribution. This conclusion is supported by absolute skewness and kurtosis values greater than 1, as well as significant results from Mardia's multivariate normality test. Consequently, a factor analysis using a polychoric correlation matrix was employed, which is considered appropriate for non-normally distributed data (Enomoto et al., 2020).

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics For The Items Of The Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37).

Item	Mean	95% IC	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis	Uniqueness
1	2.44	(2.3 - 2.57)	1.08	0.30	-0.47	0.76
2	1.88	(1.76 - 2.01)	0.99	0.81	-0.18	0.36
3	2.18	(2.04 - 2.32)	1.13	0.51	-0.78	0.34
4	2.03	(1.87 - 2.18)	1.26	1.01	-0.11	0.65
5	2.4	(2.24 - 2.56)	1.26	0.44	-0.90	0.36
6	1.84	(1.71 - 1.96)	0.98	0.72	-0.81	0.27
7	2.44	(2.29 - 2.59)	1.21	0.35	-0.84	0.37
8	2.22	(2.08 - 2.36)	1.16	0.51	-0.76	0.28
9	1.97	(1.83 - 2.11)	1.10	0.95	-0.07	0.36
10	2.17	(2.02 - 2.32)	1.19	0.65	-0.63	0.46
11	2.28	(2.13 - 2.42)	1.16	0.47	-0.73	0.37
12	2.11	(1.96 - 2.26)	1.22	0.79	-0.44	0.47
13	2.15	(1.99 - 2.31)	1.26	0.72	-0.74	0.37
14	2.16	(2.02 - 2.3)	1.16	0.62	-0.58	0.30
15	2.14	(1.99 - 2.3)	1.22	0.74	-0.56	0.28
16	1.99	(1.83 - 2.15)	1.27	1.05	-0.16	0.24
17	1.9	(1.76 - 2.04)	1.12	1.02	-0.01	0.43

18	1.98	(1.84 - 2.12)	1.09	0.81	-0.32	0.35
19	2.14	(1.98 - 2.29)	1.22	0.70	-0.62	0.31
20	1.98	(1.83 - 2.13)	1.22	1.01	-0.04	0.42
21	1.81	(1.67 - 1.94)	1.08	1.12	0.15	0.25
22	1.85	(1.71 - 1.99)	1.11	1.09	0.13	0.39
23	1.98	(1.84 - 2.13)	1.14	0.93	-0.13	0.40
24	2.3	(2.16 - 2.45)	1.19	0.52	-0.65	0.29
25	2.2	(2.05 - 2.35)	1.17	0.61	-0.59	0.24
26	2.33	(2.18 - 2.48)	1.19	0.34	-1.05	0.22
27	2.16	(2.02 - 2.31)	1.18	0.69	-0.52	0.27
28	2.24	(2.09 - 2.4)	1.24	0.62	-0.76	0.20
29	2.26	(2.1 - 2.41)	1.28	0.67	-0.66	0.27
30	2.29	(2.14 - 2.44)	1.21	0.57	-0.66	0.24
31	2.23	(2.07 - 2.39)	1.28	0.79	-0.37	0.19
32	2.17	(2.01 - 2.32)	1.25	0.78	-0.44	0.25
33	2.27	(2.12 - 2.42)	1.21	0.52	-0.71	0.18
34	2.25	(2.1 - 2.39)	1.18	0.60	-0.61	0.22
35	2.27	(2.12 - 2.41)	1.18	0.49	-0.75	0.25
36	2.43	(2.27 - 2.59)	1.29	0.45	-0.96	0.35
37	2.19	(2.04 - 2.34)	1.22	0.72	-0.49	0.29
Mardia's Test of Multivariate Normality			Value	Statistic	df	p
Skewness			502.46	20935.761	9139	< .001
Small Sample Skewness			502.46	21200.327	9139	< .001
Kurtosis			1961.09	76.242		< .001

Note: N = 250. According To Mardia's Multivariate Normality Test, The Skewness Statistic Follows A Chi-Square Distribution, While The Kurtosis Statistic Follows A Normal Distribution. The Test Results Were Significant For Both Skewness (502.46; P < .001) And Kurtosis (1961.09; P < .001), Indicating That The Dataset Deviates From Multivariate Normality.

3.3. Exploratory Factor Analysis

An Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted using a polychoric correlation matrix. Factor extraction was performed using the method of minimum residuals with an oblique Oblimin

rotation. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy was 0.97, and Bartlett's test of sphericity yielded statistically significant results (p < .001), indicating that the data were suitable for factor analysis (Lloret-Segura et al., 2014). The resulting factor loadings are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Results Of The Exploratory Factor Analysis Of The Couple Burnout Scale.

CBS-37 Item	Loading Factor			s	k
	1	2	3		
Factor 1: Indifference					
1. Criticism among us is not very constructive.	0.22	-0.20	0.44	0.30	-0.47
2. I often feel devalued by my partner.	0.17	0.04	0.64	0.81	-0.18
3. I feel that discussions are more offensive than productive.	-0.02	-0.04	0.85	0.51	-0.78
4. I act indifferent when my partner threatens me.	0.13	0.06	0.45	1.01	-0.11
5. My partner's criticisms affect my emotional well-being.	0.04	0.00	0.78	0.44	-0.90
6. My partner's offenses become recurrent.	-0.10	0.33	0.69	0.72	-0.81
7. In our arguments, words hurt more than solutions.	0.13	-0.01	0.71	0.35	-0.84
8. My partner's contemptuous attitudes generate constant discomfort.	0.05	0.04	0.78	0.51	-0.76
9. The way my partner talks to me makes me feel insecure.	0.26	0.12	0.51	0.95	-0.07
Factor 2: Reduction in Sexual Intimacy					
10. Sexual intimacy has been considerably reduced in our relationship.	0.21	0.52	0.06	0.65	-0.63
11. My partner and I no longer seek moments of physical closeness.	0.20	0.60	0.05	0.47	-0.73
12. The lack of physical contact generates discomfort between us.	-0.05	0.72	0.08	0.79	-0.44
13. Discussions affect our sex life directly.	0.05	0.65	0.16	0.72	-0.74
14. There is a clear lack of physical desire between me and my partner.	0.19	0.60	0.11	0.62	-0.58
15. I feel emotionally distant due to a lack of intimacy.	-0.05	0.85	0.07	0.74	-0.56
16. The lack of physical intimacy creates tensions in the relationship.	-0.02	0.87	0.04	1.05	-0.16
17. My partner and I no longer have private moments together.	0.20	0.56	0.05	1.02	-0.01
18. Caressing and physical contact no longer exist between us.	0.21	0.71	-0.11	0.81	-0.32
19. Lack of intimacy makes me feel rejected by my partner.	-0.11	0.91	0.01	0.70	-0.62
20. Discussions about intimacy are common between us.	0.09	0.66	0.05	1.01	-0.04
21. There is a physical disconnect that affects our emotional relationship.	0.23	0.74	-0.10	1.12	0.15
Factor 3: Unfulfilled Expectations					
22. The conversation between us has become superficial.	0.58	0.09	0.18	1.09	0.13
23. I feel that we do not share our emotions effectively.	0.55	0.12	0.16	0.93	-0.13

24. My expectations about our relationship have not been fulfilled.	0.79	0.08	-0.01	0.52	-0.65
25. I feel that my partner does not fulfill my expectations of her/him.	0.88	0.04	-0.06	0.61	-0.59
26. I am unable to achieve the goals I set for myself as a couple.	0.90	-0.02	-0.01	0.34	-1.05
27. The relationship does not meet my emotional needs.	0.87	0.03	-0.05	0.69	-0.52
28. My expectations about our future together are frustrated.	0.82	0.04	0.07	0.62	-0.76
29. I feel that my partner is unwilling to make sacrifices for the relationship.	0.82	0.03	0.01	0.67	-0.66
30. My partner's promises do not materialize into reality.	0.87	-0.03	0.04	0.57	-0.66
31. The expectations I had about love are disappointed.	0.83	0.03	0.07	0.79	-0.37
32. I feel dissatisfied with the direction our relationship is taking.	0.79	-0.05	0.14	0.78	-0.44
33. There is a disconnect between what I expected and what we experience.	0.94	-0.09	0.04	0.52	-0.71
34. The goals we share no longer seem attainable.	0.90	0.02	-0.04	0.60	-0.61
35. Expectations I had for growth as a couple are not realized.	0.81	0.06	0.02	0.49	-0.75
36. I feel that I have given more than I have received in the relationship.	0.71	0.05	0.09	0.45	-0.96
37. My expectations of happiness as a couple are diminished.	0.75	0.14	-0.02	0.72	-0.49

Note: N = 250. S = Skewness, K = Kurtosis. Factor Loadings Greater Than 0.40 Are In Bold.

The Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37), through Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), identified three factors that explain the variability in participants' responses: Indifference, Reduction in Sexual Intimacy, and Unmet Expectations. Each dimension reflects a distinct aspect of burnout within romantic relationships, and together, they account for a significant portion of the construct. This underscores the integral contribution of the present study to the understanding of couple burnout.

The first factor, Indifference, represents a core element of the construct, characterized by the absence of emotional well-being and feelings of devaluation. This component includes items that describe the impact of destructive criticism that undermines self-esteem, offensive arguments that lack productivity, and contemptuous attitudes that contribute to the deterioration of the relationship. The persistence of these negative interactions significantly contributes to emotional exhaustion and relational fragility.

The second factor, Reduction in Sexual Intimacy, consists of items that reflect a marked reduction in both physical and emotional closeness between partners. This dimension encompasses a lack of sexual intimacy, a scarcity of physical affection, and an absence of private moments shared as a couple. Such deficiencies generate discomfort, tension, and emotional distance, often resulting in feelings of

rejection and disconnection that profoundly affect the quality of the relationship.

Finally, the third factor, Unmet Expectations, comprises items that reveal individuals' dissatisfaction due to the failure to fulfill relational expectations and the discrepancy between their initial vision of the relationship and its current reality. Within this dimension, superficial communication, unfulfilled promises, and a lack of reciprocity give rise to frustration and disappointment, ultimately weakening emotional connection and undermining the couple's long-term outlook.

3.4. Confirmatory Factor Analysis

For the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), two models were evaluated: a unidimensional model and a multidimensional model. The first multidimensional model, based on the three theoretical dimensions, yielded a significant chi-square test result, suggesting an adequate model fit (CFI = 0.91, RMSEA = 0.07, SRMR = 0.04, AIC = 20853.38). In contrast, the unidimensional model, which included only a single factor, demonstrated poor fit to the data (CFI = 0.79, RMSEA = 0.11, SRMR = 0.06, AIC = 21923.29), as shown in Table 3. Additionally, the structural equation model diagram is presented in Figure 2.

Table 3: Model Fit Indices For Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Model	χ^2	df	CFI	RMSEA	SRMR	AIC
A: Unidimensional Model ^a	2515.31**	629	0.79	0.11	0.07	21923.29
B: Three-Dimensional Model ^b	1439.40**	626	0.91	0.07	0.04	20853.38

Note: N = 250. The Analysis Of 250 Responses Yielded Two Models For Evaluating 37 Items.

^a Model A included all items loading onto a single factor. ^b Model B grouped the items into three factors: Indifference (9 items), Decreased Sexual Intimacy (12 items), and Unmet Expectations (16 items). Both models were statistically significant at $p < .01$. The results are reported with chi-square (χ^2), degrees of freedom (df), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Root

Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), and Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) values.

Figure 2 presents the graphical representation of the factorial structure model of the Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37). This model identifies three main factors: Indifference (F1), Reduction in Sexual

validity analysis between the Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37) and the Couple Satisfaction Scale. Spearman’s rank-order correlation was used to

examine the degree of inverse association between the dimensions of the CBS-37 and the construct of relationship satisfaction

Table 4: Divergent Validity.

Scale	Couple Satisfaction Scale	
	r	p
Couple Burnout Scale	-0.81	< .001
D1: Indifference	-0.78	< .001
D2: Reduction in Sexual Intimacy	-0.77	< .001
D3: Unmet Expectations	-0.75	< .001

Note: N = 250. Spearman Correlations Revealed Significant Negative Relationships Between The Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37) And The Relationship Satisfaction Scale, Supporting The Divergent Validity Of The Scale.

The results reveal significant negative correlations, supporting the divergent validity of the instrument. Specifically, the overall correlation between the two scales was $r = -0.81$ ($p < .001$), indicating a strong inverse relationship. At the dimensional level, high and significant negative correlations were also observed: Indifference ($r = -0.78$, $p < .001$), Decreased Sexual Activity ($r = -0.77$, $p < .001$), and Unmet Expectations ($r = -0.75$, $p < .001$). These findings suggest that higher levels of relationship burnout are associated with lower levels of relationship satisfaction, which is consistent with the theoretical assumptions underlying the construct.

3.6. Reliability

The reliability results for the Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37) indicate that its three dimensions demonstrate excellent internal consistency. For the Indifference factor, both omega and Cronbach’s alpha coefficients were 0.92. The Decreased Sexual Intimacy dimension showed an omega of 0.96 and an alpha of 0.95. Lastly, the Unmet Expectations dimension yielded omega and alpha values of 0.98. These findings support the reliability of the CBS-37 as a robust instrument for assessing various dimensions of couple burnout (see Table 5).

Table 5: Reliability Results.

Variables	ω	α
Couple Burnout Scale		
Factor 1: Indifference	0.92	0.92
Factor 2: Reduction in Sexual Intimacy	0.96	0.95
Factor 3: Unmet Expectations	0.98	0.98

Note: N = 250. Ω = Omega Coefficient, A = Alpha Coefficient.

3.7. Conversion of Raw Scores To Percentiles

Table 6 presents the conversion of raw scores to percentiles for the dimensions assessed by the scale: Indifference, Reduction in Sexual Intimacy, and Unmet Expectations. Based on these values, cutoff points were established to classify scores into three categories: low, medium, and high. Scores at or below the 35th percentile are considered low; those

between the 35th and 65th percentiles are classified as medium; and scores above the 65th percentile are considered high. This classification system enhances the interpretability of results and facilitates the identification of cases according to the severity level within each dimension, making it a valuable tool for both clinical assessment and research purposes (Kroc et al., 2022).

Table 6: Conversión Of Raw Scores To Percentiles.

Percentile	D1: Indifference	D2: Reduction in Sexual Intimacy	D3: Unmet Expectations	Couple Burnout
5	9	12	16	37
10	9	12	16	39
15	10	12	16	41
20	12	13	17	45
25	13	14	19	48
30	13	16	24	54
35	15	17	26	58
40	16	19	28	65
45	17	21	31	71
50	18	23	33	74
55	19	24	36	80

60	21	26	40	87
65	23	28	44	94
70	25	31	46	103
75	27	34	48	107
80	28	36	51	111
85	29	38	54	119
90	31	42	57	125
95	32	46	65	139

Note: N = 250. The Table Shows The Conversion Of Raw Scores Into Percentiles For The Three Dimensions Of The Couple Burnout Scale (D1: Indifference, D2: Reduction In Sexual Intimacy, D3: Unmet Expectations) And The Total Score, Supporting The Interpretation And Classification Of Burnout Levels.

4. DISCUSSION

Recognizing couple burnout as a psychological construct is essential to understanding its impact on individual well-being and broader social dynamics (Villavicencio & Jaramillo, 2020). This phenomenon is characterized by emotional, mental, and physical exhaustion resulting from chronic relational conflict (Batres, 2016; Martínez, 2010). It manifests through feelings of frustration, decreased well-being, lack of energy, and the adoption of avoidant or confrontational behaviors. Prior studies have linked couple burnout to increased symptoms of anxiety, chronic stress, depression, and various psychosomatic disorders. It also negatively affects the quality of the emotional bond, communication between partners, and the family climate (Batres, 2016). Timely identification through appropriate measurement tools can facilitate interventions that support emotional restoration and promote healthier relational dynamics. As Pines (2013) emphasizes, unmanaged conflict and accumulated exhaustion are significant predictors of relational deterioration and family dysfunction.

Currently, various instruments are available to assess couple burnout, among which the Marital Instability Scale (MIS), developed by Boot and Edwards (2014), and the Dyadic Adjustment Scale (DAS), proposed by Spanier (1976), are particularly noteworthy. The latter has been used in recent studies to identify levels of emotional, mental, and behavioral exhaustion in conflictual marital contexts. Likewise, other instruments, such as the Maslach Burnout Inventory adapted to the couple context, have been employed to explore burnout from a psychological perspective of exhaustion (Maslach, Jackson, & Leiter, 1996). However, one of the main limitations in practice is that many of these instruments tend to focus on a predominant dimension of burnout—either emotional or behavioral—while overlooking contextual components such as the family or work environment, which influence couple dynamics. Moreover, most scales have been validated in clinical or specific populations, which limits their generalizability to

other contexts (Martínez-Pampliega et al., 2019). This highlights the need to develop and apply more integrative tools that capture the complexity of relational burnout across different stages and types of couples.

Therefore, the primary objective of the present study was to develop and determine the psychometric properties of the Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37) for young adults an instrument designed based on contemporary theories of relational dynamics and emotional deterioration within romantic contexts. The formulation of the CBS-37 and the construction of its items were grounded in recent scientific literature, as well as empirical studies addressing the factors contributing to emotional, physical, and mental burnout in intimate relationships (Pines, 2013). Following a rigorous validation process, including confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), three key dimensions were identified as components of the instrument: Indifference, Reduction in Sexual Intimacy, and Unmet Expectations. These dimensions allow for an accurate assessment of various aspects of relationship burnout, providing a comprehensive view of the phenomenon. The inclusion of these dimensions contributes to a more in-depth and context-sensitive evaluation, facilitating the early detection of signs of relational deterioration and offering a solid foundation for the design of psychological interventions aimed at restoring emotional bonds and strengthening the emotional well-being of the individuals involved.

The Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37) demonstrates strong psychometric properties, with reliable validity and internal consistency. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) identified three key dimensions Indifference, Decreased Sexual Intimacy, and Unmet Expectations which were subsequently confirmed through Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), validating the structure and improving model fit. This approach enhances the understanding provided by previous instruments, such as the Couple Satisfaction Scale (ESP-10) and the Couple Relationship Burnout Questionnaire (CRBQ), by incorporating more specific and detailed dimensions

that allow for a more comprehensive assessment of relationship burnout. The Indifference dimension captures emotional disconnection and hostile or avoidant attitudes, which are not addressed in as much detail by other instruments. The Reduction in Sexual Intimacy dimension examines the impact of diminished physical contact, a fundamental aspect often overlooked. Finally, the Unmet Expectations dimension focuses on frustration resulting from unfulfilled expectations within the relationship, an area that has received limited attention in prior research. Taken together, these three dimensions provide a more accurate and complete evaluation of couple burnout, with better statistical fit compared to other models, making the CBS-37 a valuable tool for clinical intervention in psychology and mental health setting.

Regarding the divergent validity of the Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37), significant negative correlations were observed when compared with the Couple Satisfaction Scale (ESP-10), used as an external criterion. The correlation values between the total scores of the CBS-37 and the ESP-10 ranged from -0.75 to -0.81 ($p < 0.001$), indicating a strong and statistically significant inverse relationship between the two scales. This is consistent with the theoretical proposition that relationship burnout tends to increase as marital satisfaction decreases (Huamán & Siancas, 2023). Specifically, the "Indifference" dimension of the CBS-37 showed the highest negative correlation with the ESP-10 ($r = -0.81$), suggesting that emotional distancing serves as a strong indicator of deterioration in perceived relationship quality. Following this, the "Reduction in Sexual Intimacy" ($r = -0.77$) and "Unmet Expectations" ($r = -0.75$) dimensions also showed significant correlations, though slightly lower.

It is noteworthy that, while all dimensions showed clear inverse relationships with the satisfaction scale, the "Unmet Expectations" dimension exhibited the lowest negative correlation within the set. This may be attributed to the subjective nature of this dimension, which seems to capture more introspective or idealized aspects of the relationship, such as unfulfilled desires or projections, which may not be fully reflected by broader satisfaction scales (Cano, 2022). In this regard, the lower correlation could be interpreted not as a weakness, but as evidence that the CBS-37 assesses unique aspects of relational burnout that other scales do not address with the same level of specificity.

On the other hand, the results support the added value of the CBS-37 in assessing relationship quality

from a multidimensional perspective. The clear differentiation between dimensions such as "Indifference," "Reduction in Sexual Intimacy," and "Unmet Expectations" allows for a deeper understanding of the various ways in which couple burnout can manifest. While the ESP-10 provides a global view of marital well-being (Huamán & Siancas, 2023), the CBS-37 enables the identification of specific areas of distress that may go unnoticed in more general evaluations. Therefore, the empirical evidence obtained supports the conclusion that the CBS-37 has strong divergent validity, while also providing relevant differential information for the intervention and clinical study of romantic relationships.

These findings lay the foundation for future research that deepens the understanding of burnout in romantic relationships. The importance of having a scale that assesses couple burnout through three key dimensions indifference, decreased sexual intimacy, and unmet expectations lies in its ability to provide a comprehensive and detailed view of this relational phenomenon. Each dimension allows for the identification of specific aspects of relationship deterioration. This multidimensional approach enables a more precise evaluation of the relationship's status, which supports the design of personalized therapeutic interventions. Furthermore, the development of this instrument not only addresses the need for culturally relevant tools but also opens up opportunities for conducting comparative studies, establishing risk profiles, and developing prevention strategies and methods to strengthen the marital bond. Ultimately, this scale makes a significant contribution to advancing scientific knowledge on couple dynamics and its implications for individual and collective emotional health.

4.1. Limitations

It is important and necessary to acknowledge certain inherent limitations of this study, as well as potential research directions to address them in the future. First, the sampling method used in this research was not random, which may have introduced certain biases in participant selection. Future research could employ random sampling to improve representativeness and reduce bias in the findings. Additionally, although the sample size was considerable, meeting the minimum requirements for statistical analyses, the composition of the sample was predominantly composed of young adults with specific demographic characteristics, which may limit the applicability of the results to other

populations, especially those outside the age range of 18 to 45 years. Future studies should consider larger and more diverse samples to increase the generalizability of the findings.

The exclusive use of self-reports also presents a limitation, as response biases, such as social desirability, may have influenced the way participants reported their experiences. Future research could incorporate complementary assessment methods, such as interviews or observations, to obtain a more accurate perspective. On the other hand, while solid evidence of divergent validity was obtained, the absence of a specific evaluation of convergent validity represents a limitation. Therefore, it is suggested that future studies assess convergent validity to demonstrate that this instrument measures what it claims to measure (couple burnout) by comparing it with other similar constructs.

Finally, although exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses demonstrated the multidimensionality of the scale, alternative models such as bifactor or second-order factor models were not explored. These models could help determine whether a total score that encompasses all dimensions is valid and appropriate. In future research, it would be useful to explore these models to ensure that the total score of the scale accurately represents the construct of couple burnout in its entirety.

4.2. Practical Implications

The construction and psychometric properties of the Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37) have important implications, especially in the family context. This instrument provides a specific and reliable tool to assess burnout in romantic relationships among young adults, contributing to a more accurate measurement of this phenomenon. The CBS-37 allows for the identification of key dimensions of relational deterioration, such as indifference, decreased physical intimacy, and unmet expectations. These factors serve as significant indicators of relationship burnout. Early detection through this scale facilitates the implementation of interventions aimed at restoring the relationship bond, strengthening the emotional health of both partners, and, more broadly, promoting healthier and more functional relationships in society (Villavicencio & Jaramillo, 2020). Therefore, the inclusion of the CBS-37 in clinical and research contexts enables a more comprehensive approach to couple burnout.

Couple burnout has significant implications for

both emotional health and quality of life, and the Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37) offers a specialized tool to assess this phenomenon in young adults. Its application allows for the identification of early signs of relational deterioration, facilitating timely intervention through therapeutic strategies that promote the restoration of the emotional bond and the well-being of both partners. In this way, the CBS-37 contributes to the development of comprehensive interventions aimed at preventing more severe consequences, such as conflictual breakups, family dysfunction, or deterioration in mental health.

In the educational context, the CBS-37 represents a valuable resource for university students who face the challenge of balancing their romantic relationships with academic demands. Its application helps detect how emotional burnout affects academic performance, concentration, and motivation, thus providing useful information to design strategies for emotional support and psychological guidance. In the workplace context, couple burnout can negatively impact productivity, decision-making, and organizational climate. The CBS-37, by addressing burnout from a multidimensional perspective, offers the opportunity to identify risk profiles and promote psychological support programs that favor the overall well-being of workers.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The main objective of this study was the construction of the Couple Burnout Scale (CBS-37), a self-report instrument designed to assess emotional, mental, and physical burnout in romantic relationships. The construction of the scale was carried out based on a multidimensional approach that covers key areas of burnout, such as indifference, reduction in sexual intimacy, and loss of satisfaction due to unmet expectations, which were identified through exploratory factor analysis. Regarding validity evidence, the results obtained from the confirmatory factor analysis showed that the multidimensional model of the CBS-37 provides a good fit, supporting the validity of the three proposed dimensions. Additionally, divergent validity was evidenced through significant negative correlations with the Couple Satisfaction Scale, suggesting that the CBS-37 measures a distinct construct related to burnout in romantic relationships. Concerning reliability, the internal consistency analysis revealed omega and alpha coefficients between 0.92 and 0.98, indicating excellent reliability of the instrument. These results ensure that the CBS-37 provides consistent and stable

measurements over time. As mentioned earlier, the Couple Burnout Scale is a reliable and valid instrument for assessing burnout in romantic relationships. Its solid construction, validity

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supported by factor analyses, and high reliability make the CBS-37 a useful tool in both research contexts and clinical and educational interventions.

Author contributions: **Conceptualization:** Nayely Carrión-Encarnación, Leonela Leyva-Gonzales and Paulina Quiroz-Díaz. **Methodology:** Nayely Carrión-Encarnación, Leonela Leyva-Gonzales and Paulina Quiroz-Díaz. **Validation:** Nayely Carrión-Encarnación, Leonela Leyva-Gonzales and Paulina Quiroz-Díaz. **Software:** Nayely Carrión-Encarnación, Leonela Leyva-Gonzales and Paulina Quiroz-Díaz. **Formal analysis:** Nayely Carrión-Encarnación, Leonela Leyva-Gonzales and Paulina Quiroz-Díaz. **Research:** Nayely Carrión-Encarnación, Leonela Leyva-Gonzales, Paulina Quiroz-Díaz and Marcia Romero-Vásquez. **Resources:** Nayely Carrión-Encarnación, Leonela Leyva-Gonzales, Paulina Quiroz-Díaz and Marcia Romero-Vásquez. **Data cleaning:** Paulina Quiroz-Díaz. **Writing - original draft:** Nayely Carrión-Encarnación, Leonela Leyva-Gonzales, Paulina Quiroz-Díaz and Marcia Romero-Vásquez. **Writing - revision and editing:** Nayely Carrión-Encarnación, Leonela Leyva-Gonzales and Paulina Quiroz-Díaz. **Visualization:** Paulina Quiroz-Díaz. **Supervision:** Carlos Pérez-Lara.

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ESCALA DE DESGASTE DE PAREJA (EDP-37)

Instrucciones: A continuación, encontrarás una serie de enunciados y afirmaciones sobre situaciones relacionadas con tu pareja. Marca la opción que más se asemeje a tu experiencia. No hay respuestas correctas o incorrectas, solo precisamos que respondas con sinceridad.

Utiliza el puntaje que mejor describa con qué frecuencia experimenta cada situación, según la siguiente escala:

1	2	3	4	5
Nunca	Casi Nunca	A veces	Casi Siempre	Siempre

PREGUNTAS	Nunca	Casi nunca	A veces	Casi siempre	Siempre
1. Las críticas entre nosotros son poco constructivas.					
2. A menudo me siento desvalorizado/a por mi pareja.					
3. Siento que las discusiones son más ofensivas que productivas.					
4. Actuó con indiferencia cuando mi pareja me amenaza					
5. Las críticas de mi pareja afectan mi bienestar emocional.					
6. Las ofensas de mi pareja se vuelven recurrentes.					
7. En nuestras discusiones, las palabras duelen más que las soluciones.					

8. Las actitudes despectivas de mi pareja generan malestar constante.					
9. La forma en que mi pareja me habla me hace sentir inseguro/a.					
PREGUNTAS	Nunca	Casi Nunca	A veces	Casi siempre	Siempre
10. La intimidad sexual se ha reducido considerablemente en nuestra relación.					
11. Mi pareja y yo ya no buscamos momentos de cercanía física.					
12. La falta de contacto físico genera incomodidad entre nosotros					
13. Las discusiones afectan nuestra vida sexual de manera directa					
14. Hay una clara falta de deseo físico entre mi pareja y yo					
15. Me siento emocionalmente distante debido a la falta de intimidad					
16. La falta de intimidad física genera tensiones en la relación					
17. Mi pareja y yo ya no tenemos momentos privados juntos.					
18. La caricia y el contacto físico ya no existen entre nosotros.					
19. La falta de intimidad me hace sentir rechazado/a por mi pareja.					
20. Las discusiones sobre la intimidad son comunes entre nosotros.					
21. Hay una desconexión física que afecta nuestra relación emocional.					
PREGUNTAS	Nunca	Casi Nunca	A veces	Casi siempre	Siempre
22. La conversación entre nosotros se ha vuelto superficial.					
23. Siento que no compartimos nuestras emociones de manera efectiva.					
24. Mis expectativas sobre nuestra relación no se han cumplido					
25. Siento que mi pareja no cumple con lo que esperaba de ella					
26. No logro alcanzar las metas que me propuse en pareja.					
27. La relación no cumple con mis necesidades emocionales.					
28. Mis expectativas sobre el futuro juntos se ven frustradas.					
29. Siento que mi pareja no está dispuesta a hacer sacrificios por la relación.					
30. Las promesas de mi pareja no se concretan en la realidad.					
31. Las expectativas que tenía sobre el amor se ven defraudadas.					
32. Me siento insatisfecho/a con el rumbo que toma nuestra relación.					
33. Hay una desconexión entre lo que esperaba y lo que vivimos.					
34. Las metas que compartimos ya no parecen alcanzables.					
35. Las expectativas que tenía de crecimiento en pareja no se realizan.					
36. Siento que he dado más de lo que he recibido en la relación.					
37. Mis expectativas sobre la felicidad en pareja se ven disminuidas.					

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